

THE INFLUENCE OF LEADERSHIP AND GROUP COHESIVITY ON JOB SATISFACTION AND PERFORMANCE OF THE STATE CIVIL APPARATUS OF THE REGIONAL GOVERNMENT OF NORTH KONAWE DISTRICT

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Abstract

This research aims to find out and analyze: (a)The influence of leadership on job satisfaction(b)The influence of group cohesiveness on job satisfaction, (c).The influence of leadership on performance, (d). The effect of cohesiveness on performance,(e).The effect of job satisfaction on performance(f). the role of job satisfaction in the influence of leadership on ASN performance and (g). The mediating role of job satisfaction in the influence of group cohesiveness on ASN performance. The population in this research is all State Civil Apparatus within the North Konawe Regency Regional Government Office, 60 sections consisting of 34 Departments, Agencies and Offices, 13 Regional Secretariats, 13 District Offices.The amount determined based on the Slovin formulation was 318 samples. The analysis tool used is SEM Partial Least Square (PLS). The research results show that: (a). Leadership has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. (b). Group cohesiveness has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, (c). Leadership has a positive and insignificant effect on ASN performance, (d). Cohesiveness has a positive and significant effect on ASN performance, (e) Job Satisfaction has a significant positive effect on ASN performance, (e) Job satisfaction partially mediates the influence of leadership on ASN performance and (f) Job satisfaction fully mediates the effect of group cohesiveness on the performance of Regional Government ASN North Konawe Regency.

Keywords: Leadership, Group Cohesiveness, Job Satisfaction and ASN Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Measuring employee performance in this research uses measurements based on Republic of Indonesia Government Regulation Number 30 of 2019 concerning Civil Servant Work Performance Evaluation is a systematic assessment process carried out by assessing officials on employee work targets and civil servant work behavior. Based on Republic of Indonesia Government Regulation Number 30 of 2019, assessment of civil servant work performance is carried out based on objective, measurable, accountable, participative and transparent principles. The assessment of civil servant work performance consists of elements of Employee Work Targets (SKP) and Work Behavior and is operationalized in 9 indicators, namely work quantity, work quality, time, cost, service orientation, commitment, work initiative, cooperation and employee leadership.

Furthermore, empirical support for cohesiveness is emphasized that employees who have cohesiveness will have social power where they remain in their group. Encouragement makes employees members of a group always connected and the collection of these drives makes them united. Apart from that, they feel a sense of belonging to their group and have moral feelings related to their membership in a group in the organization. Every employee in the group feels that the group is a family, team and community and has a feeling of togetherness.

Cohesive employees will also feel more attracted to their work group, have a greater desire to work together to achieve group goals and the closeness of group relationships, both physical and emotional, based on political interests that are able to reflect the strength of cohesiveness within the group to achieve organizational goals.

Alham and Idris, (2015) who conducted research on the influence of cohesiveness on performance found that there was no significant influence between group cohesiveness and employee job satisfaction, and Suriadi (2015) found that there was no significant relationship between cohesiveness and performance norms and productivity. However, in other research conducted by Mcshane & Glinow (2010), Robert C. Dailey (2009) and Ginting and Laila (2010) explained that cohesiveness has a significant effect on job satisfaction and employee performance.

It was further explained that in groups with high cohesiveness, the members also have a high commitment to maintaining the group. If group members show interactions with fellow members cooperatively, then the group has high cohesiveness, whereas in groups with low cohesiveness, on the contrary, the behavior of the members is aggressive, hostile and likes to blame their fellow members.

Work group cohesiveness is an integration within a work group which is characterized by cooperation, communication with each other, responsibility for work and the same views in order to achieve group goals. Mcshane & Glinow (2010) say group cohesiveness is an individual's feeling of attraction to the group and their motivation to stay with the group, which is an important factor in the group's success.

Apart from performance, cohesiveness is also closely related to satisfaction at work. Robert C. Dailey (2009) also found that group cohesiveness had a significant effect on job satisfaction. Mark W Aoyagi, (2011). The benefits and importance of group cohesiveness include increasing group member satisfaction. also found that group cohesiveness had a significantly positive relationship with job satisfaction.

The North Konawe Regency Government has OPDs, Services and Divisions consisting of 34 OPDs, 13 Regional Secretariats, 13 District Offices. The phenomenon of performance, leadership factors, group cohesiveness and job satisfaction are described in detail as follows:

First, based on the data obtained regarding the performance of North Konawe Regency Regional Government employees, it shows that the performance of the North Konawe Regency Regional Government has not been in accordance with the targets set, even though several SKPD have met the targets that have been set. Based on the researcher's initial observations and interviews with employees, performance assessment is not yet optimal:

- (1) The level of accuracy and thoroughness of employees in carrying out their duties, incompatibility of employee placement with the main tasks given, work standards that are still considered high by employees, the absence of independent efforts to minimize the work assigned, there are still employees who are not yet skilled in using IT equipment.
- (2) Work volume is still low due to frequent postponement of work so that the target work volume is not achieved.
- (3) Utilization of working time is not optimal, which is characterized by arrival times to the office that are often late, use of rest time that is not in accordance with rest

times and home times that are inconsistent with office hours, apart from that, employees are reluctant to work overtime and

- (4) The availability of a budget to carry out work has not been effective because what happens is that the availability of the budget that has been planned and approved is not in accordance with the programs to be implemented, so what happens is that the program follows the budget instead of the budget following the program.

The results of employee performance assessments in the last three years based on Employee Work Targets (SKP) and Work Behavior (PK) can be seen in the following table:

Table 2: Assessment based on SKP and PK in North Konawe Regency

No.	Evaluation	Average Performance Assessment 2020 – 2022			Average	Target
		2020	2021	2022		
1	Employee Work Targets (SKP)	54	51	53	40.88	60%
2	Work Behavior (PK)	34	32	33	33	40%
	Amount	88	83	86	85.66	100%

Source: North Konawe Regency BKPSDM Office processed, 2024

Based on the employee performance assessment, it appears that the average employee work target achievement can only be achieved 40.88% of the 60% target, while the average work behavior is only achieved by 33% of the 40% target achievement. The overall average assessment for the last three years from 2020 to 2022 was only 85.66%. Based on this data, it can be confirmed that the employee performance expected by the North Konawe Regency government is not as expected.

The importance of this research is based on the phenomenon that occurs within the Regional Government of North Konawe District based on the results of initial observations in several Bureaus where employee performance is not optimal. This can be seen from the following performance aspects:

The quality of employee work is still low. For example, in the Governance Section, in making facilitation and evaluation reports, sometimes they do not comply with the report format that has been provided, so they must be corrected according to the format that has been determined. Not to mention that this government bureau also manages funds sourced from the Ministry of Home Affairs' deconcentration funds, where in its implementation the activities to be carried out must be in accordance with operational technical instructions and also the timeliness of their implementation must be guaranteed.

The quantity of employee work is still low. For example, the Cooperation Section in carrying out work has still not achieved the targets that have been set. The number of targets for cooperation between regions, districts/cities, between provinces and foreign cooperation has not met the target. This is interesting to photograph because for the Southeast Sulawesi Provincial Government, building collaboration with all government stakeholders is a parameter of success in measuring the Bureau's performance.

The work completion time given to employees is still not effective. For example, the Goods and Services Procurement Bureau is often late in reporting its duties. Based on the provisions which should report the results of the realization of activities at the end of each month, in reality they are reported in the middle of the following month.

This also causes monthly performance reports to be late. Specifically for this Bureau, the performance produced by its working group (pokja) really determines how much budget absorption and development realization has been carried out by North Konawe Regency.

Based on the performance aspects mentioned above, it is suspected that this is because leadership and cohesiveness are not as expected, where the implementation of leadership is still weak and group cohesiveness is implemented well, thus affecting employee performance.

Firstly, the phenomenon related to leadership in North Konawe Regency is the egocentricity of each individual OPD leader, which causes field heads and employees to not feel satisfied, thus slowing down the process of completing tasks, in addition to that, human resource support within the OPD scope is still low, resulting in a slowdown and an impact on the mechanism and the work completion process is hampered.

Second, the real phenomenon of group cohesiveness that can be seen in the Regional Government of North Konawe Regency regarding employee behavior, especially those related to employee closeness and integration (cohesiveness) is the tendency for SKPD groups and fields or sections to still be less cohesive, a lack of interest in always joining the group field, there are still employees who do not feel part of their group, there are several employees who ask to move to another field or another agency within the scope of the North Konawe Regency Regional Government and even ask to move their assignments to another district.

The fact is that there is often a lack of synchronization between the head of the OPD and the fields within the organization, especially in planning which only involves the head of the field without conveying or informing the head of the OPD so that what the Department aims to do does not support the vision, mission and goals set. has been planned in the RPJMD so that in the implementation process sometimes the department heads do not understand the content of the activities because they are not directly involved in implementing the planning. Apart from that, some OPDs sometimes do not comply with the existing planning system in the region so that most of the central activities in the information system are not carried out.

In fact, it is hoped that the Regional Government of North Konawe Regency can create a situation that can encourage a sense of belonging, loyalty, solidarity, a sense of security, a sense of acceptance and respect as well as a feeling of success in employees which in turn can foster a sense of attachment and closeness in achieving goals. which we have aspired to together.

Another phenomenon found is that employees in field or section groups and SKPD only want to complete their own work but tend not to care about other people's work, there are employees in field or section groups who are unable to complete their work because they do not want to discuss or communicate their work to other employees. Apart from that, it was identified that there were employees in a field or section group proposing to move to another field group or even to another agency and there were employees in a field or section group carrying out their duties of their own free will, and disagreeing with policies or decisions, and even employees in the group were identified. fields or sections have different perceptions about the goals and objectives to be achieved, and still prioritize personal interests over group interests. This condition causes one of the factors that influence employee job satisfaction and employee performance. The researchers consider the above conditions to be the

justification for theoretical results and empirical studies on group cohesiveness factors that influence job satisfaction and employee performance in the North Konawe Regency Regional Government as the most dominant phenomenon, namely that the cohesiveness that occurs in the North Konawe Regency Regional Government is identified as being dominated by the presence of political interest factors. .

The results of the researcher's observations show that there is group strength from political interest factors so that the Regional Government of North Konawe Regency is able to encourage employees to have satisfaction and dissatisfaction at work and can encourage better employee performance.

This research uses job satisfaction as a mediating variable because empirically, job satisfaction as a mediation on the relationship between leadership and cohesiveness on performance was found to be inconsistent, as stated by Ratna Pudyarningsiha, et.al (2020) that job satisfaction is a partial mediation on the relationship between leadership and performance. performance, meanwhile Basir, et.al, (2023) emphasized that job satisfaction is not a mediating variable in this relationship.

Based on existing facts, many leaders have good leadership skills but employees feel dissatisfied with their leadership because they are dissatisfied. Therefore, a leader must be able to pay attention to employee job satisfaction to improve their performance. Based on this, in this research job satisfaction is placed as a mediating variable.

The various theoretical and empirical arguments and phenomena above have become the point of developing forms of research with the aim of testing and developing previous research, especially those related to variables that influence employee performance. In general, the importance of this research is that it has originality and novelty in the development of its concept.

The purpose of this research is to determine and analyze (1) The influence of leadership on job satisfaction, (2) The influence of group cohesiveness on job satisfaction (3) The influence of leadership on performance, (4) The influence of group cohesiveness on performance (5) The influence of job satisfaction on performance , (6) The role of job satisfaction in mediating the influence of leadership on performance and (7) The role of job satisfaction in mediating the influence of group cohesiveness on the performance of the North Konawe Regency State Civil Service.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The novelty of this research is development research that collaborates several research results and forms a new concept based on future research from previous research. Research by Pudyarningsiha, et.al (2020) confirms that leadership influences job satisfaction and employee performance Basir, et.al, (2023) while job satisfaction influences performance. In addition, the results show that job satisfaction mediates the influence of leadership on employee performance.

Research by Pudyarningsiha, et.al (2020) revealed the fact in his research that there are still many employees who have a low sense of togetherness and negative feelings from group members towards other groups. Therefore, it is recommended for future researchers to develop group cohesiveness as an independent variable that can increase job satisfaction and performance.

Group cohesiveness is the integration/closeness of relationships between group members to remain part of the group which is characterized by cooperation, communication with each other, responsibility for work, and the same views to achieve the organization's mission. However, the most dominant phenomenon obtained when the initial survey was carried out was that the cohesiveness that occurred in the North Konawe Regency Regional Government was identified as being dominated by the presence of political interest factors which influenced employee satisfaction and dissatisfaction in improving performance.

Regarding the group cohesiveness variable in organizations, it is still rarely researched, several studies on cohesiveness and its influence on employee satisfaction and performance still contain inconsistencies and previous research was conducted in private companies.

Johnson's (1994) opinion is that cohesive group members are more often responsible, last longer in working to achieve goals, are more motivated to complete group goals, and are more comfortable working in groups, thus influencing work satisfaction, but several other studies have found that cohesiveness has no impact on job satisfaction and performance. Al-Rawi, K. (2008), Robert C. Dailey (2009), Mark Waoyagi, et al (2011), Siti Alham and Fikri Idris, (2015) and Suriadi (2015). Based on the research study explained previously, it can be explained that cohesiveness in this research is one of the variables that can provide variations in findings so that it becomes the latest in this research.

Another novelty in the development of this research model is the existence of 3 (three) original hypotheses, including the influence of cohesiveness on job satisfaction, the influence of cohesiveness on performance and the role of job satisfaction as a mediator in the relationship between cohesiveness and performance.

The following are several definitions of leadership according to experts, including; In the book *The Art of Leadership*, Ordway Tead states that leadership is the activity of influencing people so that they want to work together to achieve desired goals. (Cartono, 2011). Robbins and Steven (2007) say that leadership is what leaders do. It is the process of leading a group and influencing it to achieve goals." So if we can conclude from the opinions above, leadership is actually how leaders can invite their employees towards organizational goals.

To measure the leadership applied to the North Konawe Regency Regional Government in this research, it refers to measurements as proposed by Hersey, Blanchard, Johnson, (2006). as follows (1) Telling, (2) Selling, (3) Participating (involving), and (4) Delegation (delegating).

Group cohesiveness is an integration within a work group which is characterized by cooperation, communication with each other, responsibility for work and the same views in order to achieve group goals, based on four indicators of work group cohesiveness proposed by Forsyth (2010), namely: social strength, unity in groups, attraction and group cooperation, political interests. The indicators of group cohesiveness are explained as follows: social strength, unity in the group, attractiveness, and group cooperation.

According to Wexley & Yukl (1989) job satisfaction is the way an employee feels about his job. This means job satisfaction as "a person's feelings towards work", which appears in the employee's positive attitude towards work and everything encountered

in the work environment. To measure job satisfaction, it is necessary to first reveal the factors that can influence job satisfaction. According to Hasibuan (2003), job satisfaction is an emotional attitude that is pleasant and loves one's job. This attitude is reflected in work morale, discipline and work performance.

According to Mathis and John H (2001), although job satisfaction is interesting and important, the most fundamental thing is the influence of job satisfaction on the organization which will affect performance.

Robbins (2001) suggests that job satisfaction is an individual's general attitude towards their work. Furthermore, Gibson (1996) stated that job satisfaction is a person's attitude towards their work, which stems from work aspects, namely wages, promotion opportunities and work environment factors such as supervisor style, policies and procedures, and working conditions.

Ivanvich, Konopaske and Metteson (2008) say that performance is related to a number of results, namely objective outcomes, personal behavior outcomes, intrinsic and extrinsic outcomes, and job satisfaction results. satisfaction outcomes).

Based on the various indicators that have been put forward, employee performance in this research is measured based on Government Regulation Number 30 of 2019 concerning Evaluation of Civil Servant Work Performance which consists of 9 (nine) indicators, namely work quantity, work quality, time, cost, service orientation, commitment, work initiative, cooperation and employee leadership. Because this research tests variables as independent variables, this research only uses 8 indicators by excluding the leadership indicator.

Based on the explanation above, a research conceptual framework was built as in Figure 1.

Scheme 1: Research Conceptual Framework

Based on the theoretical study and framework stated above, the hypothesis in this research is:

- H1 Leadership has a positive and significant influence on job satisfaction.
- H2 Cohesiveness has a positive and significant influence on job satisfaction
- H3 Leadership has a positive and significant influence on performance.
- H4 Cohesiveness has a positive and significant influence on performance
- H5 Job satisfaction has a positive and significant influence on performance.
- H6 Job satisfaction mediates the influence of leadership on performance
- H7 Job satisfaction mediates the effect of cohesiveness on the performance of the North Konawe Regency Regional Government Civil Service.

RESEARCH METHODS

This type of research falls into the category of survey research/direct observation in the field with the aim of confirming predictions made and explaining them based on facts or conditions in the field. Quantitative research has boundaries of thought, namely correlation, causality and interaction, while data objects are arranged in categorical, interphalic and continuous thought lines.

This research was conducted at the North Konawe Regency Regional Government. The research period will be carried out for 6 months starting from the completion of the proposal seminar.

The research object focuses on leadership, cohesiveness, satisfaction and performance of ASN. Meanwhile, secondary data is data that has been further processed and presented either by the primary data collector or by other parties such as SKPD profile data and data published by BPS North Konawe.

The population in this research is all Civil Apparatus within the North Konawe Regency Regional Government Office, 60 sections consisting of 34 Departments, Agencies and Offices, 13 Regional Secretariats, 13 District Offices. The number of ASNs in 60 sections consisting of 34 OPDs, Agencies and Offices, 13 Regional Secretariats, 13 District Offices, has a population of 1,540 ASNs. Based on the Slovin formula So the number of employees used as a sample for this research based on the formulation above is 318 respondents.

The data collection techniques used in this research are: Questionnaire (e-questionnaire), interviews, and literature search. The data analysis methods used in this research are descriptive statistical analysis and Partial least squares (PLS) analysis.

RESEARCH RESULT

A. Results of Analysis and Hypothesis Testing

1. Formation of Causality Relationship Path Diagrams between Constructs

The results of the relationship path diagram/structural model after processing using Smart PLS are displayed in the image/scheme1 :

Figure 1: Measurement Model (outer model and inner model)

Figure 1 shows that all of the five direct influences between the variables tested have a positive and significant effect. The complete direct effect test results are presented in Table 3

Table 3: Direct Influence Path Coefficients and Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Direct Influence	Coefficient Track	p-value	Proof
H1	Leadership (X1) -> Job Satisfaction (Y1)	0.189	0.035	+ Significant
H2	Group Cohesiveness (X2) -> Job Satisfaction (Y1)	0.734	0,000	+ Significant
H3	Leadership (X1) -> ASN Performance (Y2)	0.108	0.103	+ Not Significant
H4	Group Cohesiveness (X1) -> ASN Performance (Y2)	0.324	0.006	+ Significant
H5	Job Satisfaction (Y1) -> ASN Performance (Y2)	0.537	0,000	+ Significant

Source: Partial Least Square Output

HasThe PLS analysis in table 3 shows that; (1) leadership has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction; (2). Group cohesiveness has a significant positive effect on job satisfaction. (3) leadership has a positive and insignificant effect on ASN performance, (4) group cohesiveness has a positive and significant effect on ASN performance and (5). Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on ASN performance.

HasThis analysis proves that job satisfaction is largely determined by leadership and group cohesiveness, while ASN performance is influenced by leadership, group cohesiveness and job satisfaction.

2. Testing the Path Coefficient of Mediation Variables

Examining the influence of variables aims to detect the position of the mediating variable on the role of job satisfaction in the model. Mediation variables can be classified into three types, namely: (1) complete mediation; (2) partial mediation; and (3) not mediation Solimun, (2011).

The results of the method for examining coefficient values and the significance of the influence of mediating variables are presented in table 4 as follows:

Table 4: Path Coefficient of Mediation Influence

Hypothesis	Influence Between Variables	Indirect Influence	Direct Influence	Proof
H6	Leadership (X2) -> Job Satisfaction (Y1) > ASN Performance (Y2)	0.101	0.108	i Partial Medation
H7	Group Cohesiveness (X2) -> Job Satisfaction (Y1 > ASN Performance (Y2))	0.394	0.324	Full Mediation Mediation

Source: PLS data processing results, 2024

Based on the results of the Partial Least Square analysis, hypothesis testing is then carried out. The results of hypothesis testing can be explained as follows:

Hypothesis testing :

1. Leadership has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction.

H1 KThe path coefficient between leadership and job satisfaction is 0.189 with a p-value of $0.035 < \alpha = 0.05$. This test proves that leadership has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of North Konawe Regency Government ASN.

The better the leadership, the higher the level of job satisfaction that ASNs have. Changes in increasing leadership are positive and significant in increasing ASN job satisfaction. Thus, the hypothesis H1 stated in this research is proven to be acceptable.

2. Group Cohesiveness has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction.

H2 KThe path coefficient between group cohesiveness and ASN job satisfaction is 0.734 with a p-value of $0.000 \leq \alpha = 0.05$. This test proves that group cohesiveness has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of North Konawe Regency Government ASN.

The higher the cohesiveness, the higher the level of ASN job satisfaction that employees have. The change in increasing cohesiveness is positive and significant towards increasing ASN job satisfaction. Thus, hypothesis 2 stated in this research is proven to be acceptable.

3. Leadership has a positive and significant effect on ASN performance

H3 KThe path coefficient between leadership and employee performance is 0.108 with a p-value of $0.103 \leq \alpha = 0.05$. This test proves that leadership has a positive and insignificant effect on the performance of North Konawe Regency Government ASN. The better the leadership, the higher the level of ASN performance that employees have. Changes in increasing leadership are positive and significant in increasing ASN performance. Thus, hypothesis 3 stated in this research is proven to be rejected.

4. Group cohesiveness has a positive and significant effect on ASN performance

H4 KThe path coefficient between group cohesiveness and ASN performance is 0.324 with a p-value of $0.006 \leq \alpha = 0.05$. This test proves that group cohesiveness has a positive and significant effect on the performance of North Konawe Regency Government ASN. The higher the cohesiveness, the higher the ASN performance. Thus, the hypothesis H4 proposed in this research can be proven and declared accepted.

5. Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on ASN performance

H5 KThe path coefficient between job satisfaction and ASN performance is 0.383 with a p-value of $0.000 \leq \alpha = 0.05$. This test proves that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on ASN performance in North Konawe Regency Government ASN. The higher the satisfaction given to employees can significantly improve ASN performance. Thus, the hypothesis H5 proposed in this research can be proven and declared accepted.

6. Job satisfaction acts as a mediating influence on leadership on ASN performance

Testing hypothesis 6 (H6) job satisfaction acts as a partial mediation of the influence of leadership on ASN performance, this is proven by statistical testing which shows a path coefficient value (original sample estimate) of 0.108. This shows that job satisfaction is able to mediate the relationship between leadership and ASN performance. Thus the sixth hypothesis (H6) is declared accepted.

7. Job satisfaction acts as a mediating influence on group cohesiveness on ASN performance

Testing hypothesis 7 (H7) job satisfaction plays a positive and significant role as a full mediator of the influence of group cohesion on ASN performance, this is proven by statistical testing which shows a path coefficient value (original sample estimate) of 0.32. This shows that job satisfaction is able to act as a full mediator of the relationship between group cohesiveness and ASN performance. Thus, the seventh hypothesis (H7) which states that job satisfaction plays a mediating role in the influence of group cohesiveness on ASN performance is accepted.

DISCUSSION

1. The Influence of Leadership on Job Satisfaction

The analysis results (H1) of this study prove that leadership has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction. meaning that the better the leadership implemented by the leader, the higher the job satisfaction will be. The results of the analysis based on the outer loading value of leadership show that the indicators that must be prioritized for improvement by the Regional Government of North Konawe Regency are delegating authority and promoting so that employee job satisfaction will be higher.

The results of the structural analysis of the model with SEM-PLS to answer the hypothesis (H1) have been proven. That leadership has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. The better the implementation of leadership, the higher job satisfaction will be. The theory from Hersey and Blanchard also explains that an

effective leader is not only shown by the amount of power he has but is shown by the attention and commitment to the growth of his subordinates, so that it can improve work morale so that his performance can be further improved. Several empirical studies that are in line with this research are R. Okky Satria and HusaeriPriatna (2012) stating that one leadership style that can encourage an employee to perform well and can bring about change in the organization is the situational leadership style. Situational leadership style has a significant effect on job satisfaction. Furthermore, other research that is in line is Siti Hidayati, et. al (2015). Nurul Hidayat, et.al (2016), that leadership style has a positive effect on job satisfaction. Therefore, if the leadership style is applied effectively, it is certain to produce employees who are satisfied with their work. However, several findings that were not in line with this research were revealed by Fitria Nur Azizah, et al (2017) who confirmed that situational leadership style had no significant effect on job satisfaction.

2. The Influence of Group Cohesiveness on Job Satisfaction

Hypothesis (H2) from this research also proves that group cohesiveness has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction. This means that the higher the cohesiveness of the employee group, which is reflected through the group's social strength, attractiveness, cohesiveness of group members, unity of group members and political interests, the higher job satisfaction will be. The results of the analysis based on the outer loading value of group cohesiveness show that the indicators that must be prioritized for improvement by the Regional Government of North Konawe Regency are political interests and the cohesiveness of group members.

The results of the structural analysis of the model with SEM-PLS to answer the hypothesis (H2) have been proven. That group cohesiveness has a positive and significant effect on North Konawe Regency Government ASN Job Satisfaction. The higher the group cohesiveness, the higher the level of Job Satisfaction that employees have. This shows that the higher the factors of group social strength, attractiveness, cohesiveness of group members, and unity of group members, the higher employee job satisfaction will be.

In connection with these findings, it can be explained that the research findings prove the research hypothesis and are not in line with the research Siti Alham and Fikri Idris, (2015) who found that there was no significant influence between group cohesiveness and employee job satisfaction was not proven.

3. The Influence of Leadership on ASN Performance

The results of the analysis to answer the hypothesis (H3) cannot prove that leadership has a positive and significant effect on ASN performance. This means that the better the leadership implemented by the leadership, the higher the ASN performance will be, but the impact is not significant.

The results of the analysis based on the outer loading value of leadership show that the indicators that must be prioritized for improvement by the North Konawe Regency Government are delegating authority and promoting so that employee job satisfaction will be higher. The results of the structural analysis of the model with SEM-PLS to answer hypothesis3 (H3) have been proven. That leadership has a positive and significant effect on performance. The better the implementation of leadership, the higher employee performance will be.

The findings of this research are very relevant to variations in individual characteristics where when viewed based on age and length of service, the majority of North Konawe Regency Government ASN are in the category of high maturity and some of them are also relatively young. If this statement is related to the concept of leadership style, it emphasizes the leader's behavior with subordinates (followers) which is related to the level of maturity and readiness of the subordinates. Maturity in this case is defined as the willingness and ability of subordinates (followers) to be responsible for directing their own behavior.

The findings of this research which state that leadership has no significant effect on employee performance are not in line with research conducted by NovantriHistorika (2012) which states that situational leadership style partially influences employee performance with an influence of 28.6%. Apart from that, research by Yusmalinda (2012) confirms that leadership style partially has a positive and significant influence on employee performance, a leadership style that is in line with employee expectations will improve employee performance. Furthermore, research conducted by Dwiyanto (2001) concluded the results of his research that there was a positive and significant relationship between leadership and employee performance with a correlation coefficient of 0.588 with a significance level of 96.1%. (Anwar Serang, (2016)

4. The Influence of Group Cohesiveness on ASN Performance

The results of the analysis to answer Hypothesis 4 (H4) of this study prove that group cohesiveness has a positive and significant effect on ASN performance. This means that the higher the cohesiveness of the employee group, which is reflected through the social strength of the group, attractiveness, the cohesiveness of group members, and the unity of group members, the higher the employee performance will be.

The results of the structural analysis of the model with SEM-PLS to answer hypothesis 4 (H4) have been proven. That group cohesiveness has a positive and significant effect on the performance of the North Konawe Regency Regional Government ASN. The higher the group cohesiveness, the higher the performance of the employees. This shows that the higher the factors of group social strength, attractiveness, cohesiveness of group members, and unity of group members, the higher the employee performance will be.

Based on these findings, it can be explained that group cohesiveness by developing indicators of political interest in the cohesiveness variable developed by Forsyth (2010) that Cohesiveness is reflected through the group's social strength, attractiveness, cohesiveness of group members and the unity of group members can improve employee performance.

In connection with these findings, it can be explained that the research findings prove the research hypothesis and are not in line with the research Siti Alham and Fikri Idris, (2015) who found that there was no significant influence between group cohesiveness and employee performance was not proven.

5. The Influence of Job Satisfaction on ASN Performance

The results of the analysis to answer hypothesis 5 (H5) the influence of job satisfaction on performance based on the results of the analysis found that keJob satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on the performance of North Konawe Regency Regional Government ASN. The higher the satisfaction given to employees can significantly improve employee performance.

Empirical facts based on the results of evaluations or respondents' assessments, through indicators it was found that Job satisfaction is reflected through salary or wages is the indicator most highly perceived by employees. This means that employees are satisfied with the salary received at this time, feel that what they receive is in accordance with the workload given, satisfied with the income given, the income received is commensurate with work performance so far and satisfied with the incentives received outside of the basic salary and are in accordance with job demands.

The results of the SEM analysis of indicator measurements found that all indicators of the job satisfaction variable had a loading factor value of ≥ 0.70 . Based on the relationship between factor loadings and employee perceptions of employee job satisfaction, it was found that the most dominant contribution to the job satisfaction variable was the relationship with superiors, however, based on the mean value, this indicator was still viewed as low by employees.

Several empirical studies are in line with this research as stated by Selvam P. et.al., (2015). Which states that the relationship between job satisfaction and performance is significantly correlated. Other research that also supports previous research is Weihui Fu et.al., (2014) which states that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on performance. A person who is satisfied at work will strive to improve the quality of work and work productivity and strive to provide optimal service to the people he serves.

6. The Influence of Leadership on ASN Performance Mediated by Job Satisfaction

The results of the H6 analysis found that job satisfaction partially mediates the influence of leadership on employee performance. It means, Job satisfaction is unable to bridge the influence of leadership on the performance of North Konawe Regency Regional Government ASN. Thus, hypothesis 6 which states that job satisfaction mediates the influence of leadership on employee performance is declared proven

The application of a good leadership style makes employees independent and ready to carry out their work. This indicates that the emergence of readiness from employees will create work motivation from employees. The results of research on job satisfaction on performance have a high impact on improving performance, causing job satisfaction to be able to play a role in bridging the influence of leadership on employee performance. This is quite reasonable because the direct influence of leadership has a significant impact in improving employee performance.

Sawitri D. et.al (2016) explained that if job satisfaction has a significant influence on employee performance, then it can be concluded that job satisfaction can have a positive influence on employee performance, so the influence of any mediated variable will be able to improve employee performance.

7. The Effect of Group Cohesiveness on ASN Performance Mediated by Job Satisfaction

The results of the analysis of hypothesis 7 found that job satisfaction acts as a full mediating variable in the influence of group cohesiveness on employee performance. It means, Job satisfaction is able to bridge the influence of group cohesiveness on the performance of North Konawe Regency Regional Government ASN employees. Thus, hypothesis 7 (H7) which states that job satisfaction mediates the effect of group

cohesiveness on employee performance can be proven to be accepted. Variable measurement resultsThe construct of group cohesiveness consists of five indicators, namely: social strength of the group, attractiveness, cohesiveness of group members, unity of group members and political interests. Based on the results of the PLS analysis test, it is confirmed that the five variable indicators have an important role or large contribution to the formation of the group cohesiveness latent variable in the North Konawe Regency Regional Government. The most dominant indicator is the indicator of political interest, followed by group cohesiveness, social strength, attractiveness and the lowest is the unity of group members.

The results of this research prove that group cohesiveness has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction. This means that the higher the cohesiveness of the employee group, which is reflected through the group's social strength, attractiveness, cohesiveness of group members, unity of group members and political interests, the higher job satisfaction will be. Likewise, the direct influence of group cohesiveness is that the higher the cohesiveness, the higher the employee performance will be.

However, several previous studies are not in line with the findings of this study, as confirmed by Zulkifli, et.al (2017) in their research who found that group cohesiveness has a strong relationship with performance, mediated by job satisfaction. Alham, et.,al (2015) found that group cohesiveness has a significant influence on employee performance and the role of job satisfaction is very large in mediating group cohesiveness and employee performance. Murti, Herry and Veronika Agustini. (2013) also found that group cohesiveness has a significant effect on performance through job satisfaction.

Research Findings

Based on the results of data analysis and discussion, theoretical and empirical studies of this research found that:

1. Group cohesiveness is a variable that has a positive and significant influence on job satisfaction and has the highest path coefficient to increase job satisfaction. Apart from that, group cohesiveness is a variable that has a positive and significant impact on employee performance.
2. Job satisfaction acts as a partial mediating variable on the influence of leadership on the performance of North Konawe Regency Regional Government ASN
3. Job satisfaction acts as a full mediating variable on the influence of group cohesiveness on the performance of North Konawe Regency Regional Government ASN

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

Based on the research results, several conclusions can be formulated as follows:

- 1) Leadership has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction.
- 2) Group cohesiveness has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction.
- 3) Leadership has a positive and insignificant effect on ASN performance.

- 4) Group cohesiveness has a positive and significant effect on ASN performance.
- 5) Job satisfaction has a significant positive effect on ASN performance
- 6) Job satisfaction acts as a partial mediating variable for the influence of leadership on the performance of North Konawe Regency Regional Government ASN.
- 7) Job satisfaction acts as a full mediating influence on group cohesiveness on the performance of North Konawe Regency Regional Government ASN.

Suggestion

Based on the results and conclusions of this research, the following suggestions can be put forward as recommendations for this research:

1. Leaders need to give confidence in employees' abilities to carry out work, delegate authority to subordinates when the leader is not there and give authority to subordinates to make decisions regarding their responsibilities.
2. Leaders must recognize employees who have high work abilities, appreciate employees who have broad insight, give praise when employees are able to carry out their duties well and acknowledge the achievements and dedication achieved by employees. Apart from that, leaders must encourage subordinates to continue to work together and feel that what is done and produced is a shared responsibility so that employees are increasingly motivated to complete the work.
3. Encourage increased employee performance through increasing employee commitment and work quality, especially the ability to complete tasks carefully according to the quality of the planned work
4. Encourage employees to have group responsibilities that are greater than personal responsibilities, emphasize the need to try to help other groups who are having problems, always maintain a sense of belonging and togetherness, always maintain commitment in any situation, have the ability to collaborate in groups and have the skills to maintain cohesiveness in group.
5. The need for leaders to provide direction to subordinates, strengthen communication relationships between superiors and subordinates in completing work, leaders are always willing to take the time to help if employees experience difficulties, always provide opportunities for employees to convey ideas and input, be objective in assessing employee work performance and be consistent in implement the applicable rules, even though some employees consider their implementation to be not optimal
6. Suggest to future researchers to study job satisfaction and modify indicators and conduct studies both as independent variables that influence performance and as mediation or moderation in an effort to realize better performance.

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